

ALLOCATION OF RESPONSABILITIES ON DATA TREATMENT ON RELATIONSHIP WITH SOFTWARE ENGINEER

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Abstract:

A Software Engineer, notwithstanding its assigned contract-level, is responsible of , an at least, one software countermeasure. Besides, it shall be appointed other safeguards related to the first one, drawing a map which must be invoked by files managed by e- mails and their correlatives digital firms. Both, Software Project Management and Incidence repsonsabilities encounter practical solutions in this article.

Keywords:

asset, data management, countermeasure, project management

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I. A Security Document

Trying to meet the equilibrium between the essence of data and its technical countermeasures, thus explicitly will assume the different security levels we can admit in an e-Governmental Software Application; In this case and considering the State of Art, we must invoke the Security Schemas for each Nation, and on the acknowledgement that behind these perspectives international standards shall be monitored and traced.

The specification of a "requisite"¹ literally converts it in an asset² of the ISMS, *Information Management Security System*³, underlying the following premise: no information security break should no generate an important economic measurable damage.

The *SLA, Service Level Agreement*⁴, clarify those technical safeguards that will justify possible incidences , establishing a possible dialogue between the categorized clauses in each type of normalized standard, named arbitrarily in ISO 27001, as the following:

- Security Policy
- Information Security Management
- Assets Management
- Medioambiental and Physic Security
- Access Control
- Acquisition, Development and Maintenance of the Information System
- Incidence Management
- Compliance

Whereas each security category will have, at least, one technical countermeasure in order to reach the goal of the identified "asset", the achievement of the security clauses will repose on such legendary basements:

1 Engineering Standards Committee of the IEEE Computer Society, IEEE Recommended Practice for Software Requirements . IEEE Std 830-1998. Software , (pg.10.)

2 ISO/IEC 27 001. Information Technology Security Techniques. Information Security Managenent Systems. Requirements. Términos y Definiciones. 3.1 Activo: cualquier bien que tiene valor para la organización

3 ISO 27 001. Introduction and cl. n° 4

4 ISO 27001, 8. 1.3

- Adequacy on Legal Requirements
- Security Knowledge

Besides, we must consider as a monitoring task, and at the European area the *Excellence Framework of the electronic Administration*, denoted as CAF⁵, and whose 2014 version is published to motivate and give support to the practised interoperability between the different Administrations in voluntarily collaboration.

In 1978 'The Vancouver Group' organized an important encounter for the medical media, whose work would be followed by the creation of the *ICMJE, International Committee of Medical Journal Editors*⁶, and its annual published ethic principles, named as *Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals*.

This group develops a significant premise on the importance of the existence of an unique and isolated clinical data⁷. If all the following dissertation upon an analysis on a juridical european instrument aiming the supervision of personal data treatment, i.e. The *Security Document*, seems to be insignificant, we will be unable to undertake the consequences of its uniqueness or more explicitly exposed non only administrative punishment shall be applied.

On the Subject that a possible *Document Index Description*⁸ might be exposed as the following:

1.- **Format and Scripting**

With respecting the *Security Levels* observed from previous Auditory Traces, the *Entity Data Model* shall reflect these new changes and perspectives. Furthermore, it will be pointed out the specified Framework (operational, safeguards environment, ..) , within the achievements were found. Nevertheless, the Format of the Scripting should always be conditioned to the following chances:

5 CAF, Common Assessment Framework

6 EIPA, European Institute of Public Administration

7 Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, WP n° 223.

8 "Guía de Seguridad de Datos". *Agencia Española de Protección de Datos*

- a) the Security Levels
- b) the classified Technical and Operational Safeguards
- c) a Security Document for each File destined for Monitoring Data Treatment
- d) a Generic Document involving all the Files destined for Monitoring Data Treatment

Under the condition of not reaching a related safeguard, we must explicitly determine its identification and alternative if possible, but in all cases registered as a failure.

2.- Access Politics: Registers

Private and Public Access is underlined firstly to overcome the internal and complex infrastructure inside the Governmental e-Section, with the plus of the aggressive outsourcing activity. It may appear new hardware specifications, for example, in order to increase the security of the Interoperability Layer (Biometric, etc,.). The trazability of the access process through a concretedigital service must assure the minimal periodicity change over analysed identities.

3.- Supports: Selection and Hosting

It is under our responsibility, that it is to say, under the Controllers or the Processors⁹ to register the minimal movement, either from the logical (Files) or physical supports (devices) with or without artificial intelligence within, notifying:

- a) the classified level of access
- b) the date and ubication of the trace
- c) human resource identification, responsible of the registry
- d) derivation of the related safeguards involved

⁹ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party of the European Data Protection Directive, WP n° 195: "Working Document 02/2012 setting a table with the elements and principles to be found in Processor Binding Corporate Rules"

A more abstract conceptualization of a software support is provided with a strict orientation to other forms of classification and subsequent applied levels of security that necessarily shall have to be conformed both in emails and the digital firm

4.- ***Data Model: Data Label Standards***

We can afford it underlying a concrete clause from ISO 27799, control 7.2.2. :

<<Identifying and where appropriate protectively assets as confidential can be an important tool in staff training and in policy compliance. This works best when the classification acts as an indicator of required information handling compliance. The classification may also be an important component of data protection agreements among jurisdiction and with third-party organization and their staff. The identification and labelling of information assets is also an essential component of ISO/IEC 27002, >>

The documented *Data Model* will be automated to suffer the undertaken deletion an updated processes in order not to duplicate data, and to encounter the appropriate correspondence between the logical supports and its classification in the audited *Inventory* or in some environments known as *Repositories*¹⁰.

5.- ***Quality Management Assessment: HW and SW***

With a previous perspective of Technical Implemented Procedures, we can incorporate part or the whole of them in dependants of some concrete sections:

- internal and external auditories
- incidences notifications
- recovery backups
- supports tracing
- data encryption
- desleal access

10 COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS. "Towards interoperability for European public services". COM(2010) 744 final. Recommendation 11th

It is the responsibility of the *Software Engineer*¹¹ to decide the order in which the criteria will be followed and audited and the format of managing the volume of quality procedures.

6.- Software, Sw, Logic Units: Files

Confidentiality as a dimension of security may be exposed by the alteration of transient information by ways of injection or detention, for example .Our instrument shall reflect:

- regulations and laws that directly will affect the file
- datatype specifications splitted by its analogous countermeasures
- files incidence monitory responsibility classified by their human resources relationships
- Informatic System Configuration

The Regulatory Authority will account the registries of the classified files in a proper way.

7.- Periodicity: Reports

By a Procedure it will be determined the logs that are of our interest an the periodicity of the registry auditory with a level of detail that will have a correspondence with the "Risk Management Plan Activity".

8.- Regulatory Bodies and Standards (Applied Semantic)

Some statistical conclusions might be derived from the Life Cycle of the data manipulated by the *e-Administration*. And the implicit semantic rules that accompanies each levelled phase might be observed not to wholly commit negligence in their lecture:

11 IEEE Software Committee, SWEBOK

- *incidence resolution* in juridical and jurisdictional conformance inside the *e-Section*
- *order* by which it shall no motivate a difference on the incidence treatment between the classified risks and those only estimated by the security levels
- *incidence resolution impact*

9.- *Data Treatment: Supervision and Monitoring Responsibility*

The three Security Dimensions, Disponibility, Confidentiality, Integrity and Traceability must appoint to the responsables of the technical safeguards, distinguishing from the affected human resource

10.- *Auditory*

From the deduction that it is really impossible to consider and treat all the technical items associated with the collection of assets and their risks involved, it is essential to conclude the compendium of events that will take part in the auditory. It must be considered a practical solution to recognize the interrelation between the different software life cycle documents and the rationalised and documented items derived from the process.

II. Its relationships with the WP 195 Gt29 document

On the premise that the Criteria for WP 195 is exposed on criteria 2.2 of the Working Paper Gt29 WP 195, D 95/46/CE, we can develop a working framework that simplifies the document from the point of view of *Project Management*¹²:

12 Project Management Institute, PMI, Norma Americana Nacional ANSI. "PMBOK, Guía de los Fundamentos de la Dirección de Proyectos." 3º Edición., 2004

premise of the Project	
Criteria 2.4	The creation of a network of privacy officers or appropriate staff for handling complaints and overseeing and ensuring compliance with the rules
DPAs ¹³ identification and competences	
Criteria 2.2	The existence of a complaint handling process for the BCR ¹⁴
way to expose the case based on WP 195	
Criteria 1.8	There is easy access to BCR for data subjects and in particular easy access to the information about third party beneficiary rights for the data subject that benefit from them
express reference order to developed Taxonomy	
Criteria 1.6	The company has sufficient assets
Criteria 1.4	Responsibility towards the Controller
Criteria 1.7	The burden of proof lies with the company not the individual

Table 1. Project Management resume

Besides, we can appoint its relationship with the developed *Security Document Indexes* in the previous section:

Table 2. Security Document vs. WP 195 criteria en Project Management perspective

CRITERIA FOR BCR	ALLOCATE RESPONSABILITY	Security Relationship-indexes	Document
1.4.	On both sides the Controller will meet the defence of his rights, and the responsibilities of his duties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8(REGULATORY BODIES AND STANDARDS (APPLIED SEMANTIC)) 9(DATA TREATMENT: 	

13 Data protection Authorities

14 Article 29 Data Protection Working Party of the European Data Protection Directive, WP n° 107, "Working Document setting forth a Cooperation Procedure for Issuing Common Opinions on Adequate Safeguards from Binding Corporate Rules"

WP n° 133, "Recommendation 1/2007 on the Standard Application for Approval of Binding Corporate Rules for the Transfer of Personal Data"

WP n° 153, "Working Document setting a table with the elements and principles to be found in Binding Corporate Rules"

WP n° 154, "Working Document setting a framework for the structure of Binding Corporate Rules"

WP n° 155, "Working Document on Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) related to Binding Corporate Rules"

WP n° 204, "Explanatory Document on the Processor Binding Corporate Rules"

		SUPERVISION AND MONITORING RESPONSABILITY)
1.6	An Application Form must be establish on the chain of liabilities between the Controller and the Processor, independently of the establishment of the Data Base,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7(PERIODICITY: REPORTS), • 8(REGULATORY BODIES AND STANDARDSS (APPLIED SEMANTIC)
1.7	The discharge of responsibility lays, firstly, on the acceptance of liability between the members of the group and secondly, on the probe that the members of the signaturred BCR has no committed any breach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4(DATA MODEL: DATA LABEL STANDARDS), • 6(SW LOGIC UNITS: FILES), • 7(PERIODICITY: REPORTS)
1,8	there is a specific allusion to both parts of a Taxonomy, that it is to say, pointing out to a concrete support : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the data subject: the Web of the BCR • Access for the Controller: The SLA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5(QUALITY MANAGEMENT ASSESSMENT: HW AND SW)
2,2	The equilibrium between the two appointed taxonomies is dealt with a concrete manageable treatment process as follows for the claim: <i>data subject-> handling process for the BCR discrete functions->Processor Group(possibly a Department)->Controller->Data Protection Authority->Court</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8(REGULATORY BODIES AND STANDARDS (APPLIED SEMANTIC)
2,4	The requirement of a top management support to oversee and ensure compliance with the rules is relied on an appropriate staff at both sides, global and local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2(ACCESS POLTICS: REGISTERS), • 9(DATA TREATMENT: SUPERVISION AND MONITORING RESPONSABILITY)

Analysing¹⁵ the Document numbered as *WP n° 195 of the Gt29 Workshop Group on respect of*

15 Furthermore reading through the Workshop Gt29 Documents, explicitly appoints to the deserted conclusion: Article 29 Data Protection Working Party of the European Data Protection Directive, WP 218 . “Statement on the role of a risk-based approach in data protection legal frameworks “ : << Compliance should never be a box-ticking exercise, but should really be about ensuring that personal data is sufficiently protected. How this is done, may differ per controller. Data subjects should have the same level of protection, regardless of the size of the organisation or the amount of data it processes . The so-called “risk-based approach” is not a new concept, since it is already well

D 95/46/CE , we agree with them that, at least, it must be considered four optimized levels on the 'Allocate Responsibility Decision'. If , due to the size of the Enterprise it was impossible to develop this scheme, we can, still, invoke each functionality with the assumed premise that an only responsible must consider both the Software Engineer Profile and that of a legal counsel on Data Treatment:

1. The *Controller*: the one who is able to lodge a complaint before the DPA or Courts to the Data Protection Subjects
2. The EU Member *Processor*: the one who remedies breaches caused in or outside EU Countries
3. The *Sub-Processor*: the one who guaranteed data processing facilities for auditing of the processing activities
4. The *Software Engineer*: the one who ensures compliance at local level (see previous Sw application assumption)

III. Support to ARCO Rights execution and Conformance with the ISO/IEC 27001-02 standards

We can propose two methods to express the difficulty and complexity that is implicitly formulated on the Decision of "Allocate Responsibility" on Data Treatment , furthermore, on an Environment of transferences to third countries:

known under the current Directive 95/46/EC especially in the security (Article 17) and the DPA prior checking obligations (Article 20). The DPAs' role with respect to the risk-based approach will namely consist of: - updating the list of processing which can be considered to present specific risks by essence (Article 33 of the draft regulation), - developing guidelines on impact assessments and on other accountability tools (as the CNIL and the ICO did with their privacy risk management methodology), - carrying out enforcement procedures in case of non compliance of controllers, which may imply challenging risk analysis, impact assessments as well as any other measures carried out by data controllers, - targeting compliance action and enforcement activity on areas of greatest risk. >>

a) *A Software Application Specification that gives support to ARCO Rights execution*

Thinking on a *Test Software Application* we might think on a Framework whose control-frame-results will be pictured as the following:

- With independence of the development in the *Software Life Cycle* of a Treatment Data Application in a *e-Section*, we need to give support to an ARCO(Access, Rectification, Cancellation and Omission) *Right*
- For each of the *ARCO Rights*, it will be implemented a method (not in an administrative way) for the isolated trigger that treats the right in solicitude, monitoring, subsequently, the mechanisms of heritage, interfaces and abstraction
- There shall be counted as much as four methods, each for each right, implemented on those languages that co-exist within the Production e-Section Software
- Through a 'white-cage test' the differences between the times carried out by the "Access Profiles" shall be written down reflecting the invocations of the Software Components that uses the indicated method
- Optimization of the control-frame-time-results shall be traced, splitting and considering, firstly, the different *Access Profiles* and, secondly, the practised Languages. Summing up these premises to the schedule of the Trigger, named traditionally as an *Agent* of the Database Management, the line for each language will be drawn and distinguished
- both, via the Client and via the Server, the Software Application

Description shall be concluded

Paying some attention through the ISMS Standard ISO 27001 that it doesn't commit negligence with considerations upon P(Plan).D(Do).C(Check).A(Act), and *on* the Supervision of our ARCO method , we could meet alongside some more conclusions and relationships.

When we select a "Technical Safeguard", it is remarkable to increase the observance on the Scene the manner the Access User/Profile interacts and at which times and conditions, taking in consideration:

- Design Analysis
- Profile/User's Use Case
- Database Design Context (update and data crossing)
- Countermeasure Design derivation; through incidence treatment and differences on his given orientation (proactive, corrective, etc)
- An Erroneous Management is proposed to be sizeable in order to monitor the conformance index on Observance Attention of a concrete incidence. This concluded Erroneous Management Analysis might lead us to the correct application of the "Excellence Framework"

The Flow of Communications must leads us to the exposure of that an 'Erroneous Management' and also it will drive us till the specified method test. It also must be appreciated that the jump from the both Plan Incidence and Risk Management is not considered the better approximation to the Excellence Framework. This

posture may be clarified through concrete clauses of the following standards

b) *Conformance with the ISO/IEC 27001-02 standards*

The Equipment of the Software Engineer who works on the Support of a Four Levels Framework must also take into account the premises exposed in the following international standards, as an example on the area of the e-Health:

- { ISO/IEC 27002 }
Health Informatics-Information Security Management in Health. Code for the Practice of the Information Security Management.
- I ISO/IEC 27001: } *information Technology. Security Techniques. Information System Management Security (ISMS) Requisites*
- { ISO/IEC 17799 } *Information Technology. Security Techniques on e-Health Information Systems*

ISO/IEC no.	Clause number and description	Details
<i>ISO/IEC 27002</i>	7.10 Security Information Incidence Management 7.10.1 Security Information Weaknesses and Incidence Reporting	Organizations involved in 'Health Care' must develop Procedures in order to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • give quick and methodological support to the probable incidents • produce effective actuations at right times and circumstances • bundle adequate information to generate, i.e. Auditory Logs, etc We must no obviate that Security Information Incidents considers, also, Personal Corruption and the inhabilitation of part or total SI, so we must reinforce the Patient Security. The standard appoints to regular evaluation of the Countermeasures and Risk Assessments sizing its

		efficacy.
<i>ISO/IEC 27001</i>	7. Information System Management System 's Revision	Management Data must contemplates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISMS Revisions • Techniques, Products and Procedures dedicated to improve the behaviour and efficacy of the ISMS • The State of the Corrective and Preventive Countermeasures • Efficacy Patterns results • The Following of the Previous Versions
<i>ISO/IEC 17799</i>	13.Management on a Security Information Incidence 13.2. Security Information Incidence and Improvements Management 13.2.1 Responsibilities and Procedures	The Procedures must include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis and Identification of the incidence cause • Specification and Implementation of the Corrective Action for avoiding recurrence A misleading in the Taxonomy interpretation may derive on erroneous human resource selection and operation

Table 3. ISO 27001-02 relationships

IV. Conclusions

On the Framework of the Transferences to Third Countries we must not obviate that we are leading with private businesses , although some electronic administrative processes shall be taken into account in the respective state involved. The Excellence achieved in the e-Administration shall reflect the grade of Transparency of its activities and legal duties. Nevertheless, the complexity of the privacy affair might takes note of the corrective countermeasures in order to protect the whole process